

Terpenoids Part L. A New Synthesis of dl-Sabinene

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The copper catalysed decomposition of 1-diazo-5-isopropyl-hex-5-ene-2-one furnishes Sabina ketone which on submission to Wittig's reaction with triphenyl methyl phosphonium iodide yields dl. sabinene.

In continuation of our synthetic studies¹⁻² involving the decomposition of properly substituted olefinic α -diazo ketones³⁻⁴ for the preparation of the key intermediates, polycyclic ketones with a cyclopropane ring in conjugation with $>C=O$ group, we have extended this technique for developing a new synthesis of dl.sabinene which forms the subject matter of the present communication.

Sabinene⁵⁻⁶, a bicyclic monoterpene with a cyclopropane ring has been found in a wide variety of essential oils e.g., Savin Oil⁷, lavandin oil⁸, juniperus horizontalis oil⁹ and citrus oils¹⁰, while sabina ketone is present in lavandin oil¹¹.

A total synthesis of sabinene (I) has been recently reported¹² through the action of methylene iodide in the presence of Zn-Cu couple (Simons-Smith reagent) on the α , β -unsaturated cyclopenta-ene-ol, followed by oxidation and Wittig's reaction. However, in the present studies, a new synthesis of dl sabinene has been effected and the following scheme illustrates the sequence of

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reactions employed :

Ethyl- α -isopropyl acrylate (III), the starting material, was obtained by the method of Nazarov and coworkers¹³. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction¹⁴ of the ester (III) in ether provided 2-isopropyl-allyl alcohol (IV) in 55% yield. With ethyl vinyl ether, the allyl-carbinol (IV) was converted¹⁵ into its vinyl ether (V) in the presence of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate as a catalyst. The purified ether (V) on Claisen rearrangement¹⁶ in a sealed tube in an atmosphere of nitrogen, generated 4-isopropylpent-4-ene-1-al (VI) in 65% yield. The aldehyde (VI) was oxidised to its corresponding acid (VII) with silver nitrate¹⁷ in good yield. The acid (VII), on treatment with thionyl chloride in benzene gave the acid chloride (VIII) in quantitative yield. 3-Isopropyl-pent-3-ene-ol chloride (VIII) when reacted with ethereal solution of diazomethane¹⁻⁴, yields 1-diazo-5-isopropyl hex-5-ene-2-one (IX) which on decomposition with anhydrous copper sulphate in refluxing cyclohexane¹⁴ furnished sabinone (II). The ketone (II) when subjected to Wittig's reaction with triphenyl methyl phosphonium iodide according to the conditions as laid down by Corey and co-workers¹⁸, formed dl.sabinene in good yield. The synthetic hydrocarbon was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina. The identity of the hydrocarbon was established through the comparison of its I.R. spectrum with that of natural compound¹⁹.

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19. Infrared spectrum of the natural occurring sabinene was kindly supplied by Dr. S. K. Freeman, International Flavours and Fragrances Inc., U.S.A.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Isopropyl-allyl alcohol (IV): To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (5.70 g.) in ether (305 ml.), was added dropwise with stirring, the unsaturated ester (III, 28.4 g.), in ether (200 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. After cooling, the mixture was decomposed with sodium potassium tartrate (10%, 200 ml). The organic material was extracted thrice with ether, dried and solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation under diminished pressure yielded the carbinol (IV, 11.0 g., 55%). b.p. 60–65/25–30 mm; $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4801$ I.R. : 3500, 1030 cm^{-1} (–OH), 1650 and 892 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$). (Found C, 71.48; H, 15.58. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 72.00; H, 12.00%).

2-Isopropyl-allyl vinyl ether (V): A mixture of the carbinol (V) (10.0 g.), freshly crystallized mercuric acetate (1.5 g.) and ethyl vinyl ether (52.0 g.) was refluxed for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath and stirred for 30 min. with cold sodium carbonate solution (10%, 25 ml). The organic phase was separated and dried over (K_2CO_3). The excess ethyl vinyl ether was evaporated and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the vinyl ether (V, 10.1 g., 79% yield), b.p. 50–55/40–42 mm. The vinyl ether (V) was further purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and eluted with petroleum-ether (40–60). $\eta_D^{18} = 1.4251$.

I.R. : 1640, 1625, 1175 cm^{-1} (vinyl ether) and 920 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$). (Found : C, 75.74; H, 10.69. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires, C, 76.18; H, 11.11%).

4-Isopropyl-pent-4-ene-1-al (VI): $\sqrt{\text{The vinyl ether (V, 9.4 g.) was heated for } \frac{1}{2} \text{ hr. at 180–190 in an atmosphere of nitrogen in a half filled sealed tube, fully immersed in an oil bath. Direct distillation afforded the aldehyde (VI) (6.0 g.; 65\% yield), b.p. 60–62/35 mm. I.R. 2740, 1720 } \text{cm}^{-1}$ * (–CHO); 920 and 890 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$). $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4458$.

The aldehyde readily gave 2 : 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative melting at 62°. (Found, N, 27.48. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires, N, 27.98%).

4-Isopropyl-pent-4-ene-oic acid (VII): To a solution of the aldehyde (VI, 6.1 g.) in ethanol (250 ml) and silver nitrate (6.5 g.) in distilled water (160 ml), was added during 1 hr. with stirring, a solution of sodium hydroxide (6.5 g) in distilled water (320 ml). After stirring for 3 hr. at room temperature the reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated in vacuum. Unreacted material was taken up in ether, acidification in the cold of the aqueous phase with dilute sulphuric acid gave the acid as a thick oil which was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent and distillation of the residue under reduced pressure gave the acid (VII, 4.2 g., 60% yield), b.p. 85–90/25–30 mm. $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4905$ (Found : C, 67.14; H, 9.29. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires, C, 67.6; H, 9.86%).

4-Isopropyl-pent-4'-ene-oyl chloride (VIII): A solution of the above acid (VII, 3.6 g.) and thionyl chloride (4.5 g) in benzene (50 ml) was refluxed till the evolution of hydrochloric acid gas had ceased. Excess of the solvent and the thionyl chloride were removed under vacuum and the acid chloride was used without further purification.

* Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis by B.M. Anand and L. K. Khuller, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. absorption spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infracord with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid film.

Sabina ketone (II): A solution of the acid achloride (VIII, 3.0 g) in ether (20 ml) was added to an ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from 7.0 g. N-nitrosomethyl urea. The solution was left for 2 hr. at room temperature and the solvent and excess of diazomethane removed yielding a yellow oily product. I.R. absorption spectrum showed characteristic absorption bands at 2100 and 1640 cm^{-1} (diazoketone). A suspension of the diazoketone in cyclohexane (60 ml) and anhydrous copper sulphate (1.0 g $^{\frac{1}{2}}$) was heated under reflux for 18 hr. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solvent evaporated to produce the desired ketone (II). I.R. spectrum of the residual ketone (II) showed the absence of the absorption bands characteristic of α -diazo-ketone.

Sabina ketone (II) was chromatographed over neutral alumina (elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60)-benzene, 10 : 1). I.R. spectrum showed characteristic absorption bands at 3055, 1725, 1165, 1025, 920 and 810 cm^{-1} . Lit¹² reports similar peaks at 3060, 1730, 1160, 1030, 920 and 795 cm^{-1} . $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4682$. (Found : C, 77.84; H, 9.75. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$, requires : C, 78.22; H, 10.14%).

dl.Sabinene (I): A solution of methyl sulphinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (1.1 g., 50%) and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphoxide (7.5 ml.). The solution was cooled in a cold water bath and stirred during addition of methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (5.8 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (15 ml.) when the reddish colour of methylene triphenyl phosphorane was produced. After stirring for 15 min., the ketone (II, 1.1 g) in T.H.F. (10 ml) was added and stirred overnight. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water and extracted with petroleum ether washed thrice with water. After the removal of the solvent, the residue was percolated through a neutral alumina column and eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60). The solvent was evaporated and the residue on distillation furnished dl. sabinene (I, 0.89 g., 70% yield). I.R. : 3060, 1650, 1495, 1450, 1400, 1350, 1325, 1300, 1275, 1255, 1195, 1150, 1130, 1095, 1075, 1030, 990, 970, 950, 930, 860, 810, 760, and 740 cm^{-1} . Lit. reports^{12,19} I.R. : 3080, 1675, 1485, 144, 1385, 1365, 1320, 1300, 1275, 1245, 1200, 1160, 1135, 1090, 1070, 1025, 990, 960, 945, 925, 870, 810, 780 and 735 cm^{-1} . $\eta_D^{19} = 1.4705$. Lit. reports¹² 1.4681. (Found : C, 87.84; H, 11.35. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$: C, 88.24; H, 11.76%).

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